

Розглядаються науково-теоретичні основи та практичне значення диференційованого підходу до формування професійних компетенцій у студентів вищих педагогічних закладів. Обґрунтовується необхідність врахування індивідуальних особливостей студентів, стилів навчання та професійних інтересів у процесі підготовки вчителів. Диференційований підхід підвищує рівень професійної компетентності, розвиваючи креативність, відповідальність та рефлексивні здібності студентів, а також сприяючи мотивації, автономності та адаптивності в професійному контексті. Отже, стаття пропонує науково-методологічні основи для впровадження компетентнісного індивідуалізованого навчання у вищій педагогічній освіті та сприяння підготовці інноваційних, рефлексивних та особистісно-орієнтованих вчителів.

Ключові слова: професійна компетентність, диференційований підхід, вища освіта, здобувач вищої освіти, педагогічна діяльність, рефлексія, індивідуалізоване навчання.

Стаття отримана 4.10. 2025
Стаття прийнята 26.10. 2025
Опублікована 26.12. 2025

UDC 373.3:37.015.3

MAIN FACTORS DETERMINING THE PERSONALITY-ORIENTED PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Aida Zeynalova BABAK – Doctoral Student,
Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7179-7842>
doi
aide.90@icloud.com

The article examines the essence and implementation mechanisms of personality-oriented educational technologies in primary school teaching. It highlights that ensuring a personality-centered approach in the learning process requires the teacher's pedagogical competence, creative activity, and ability to adapt instructional content to students' individual needs and developmental characteristics. The study emphasizes that effective realization of personality-oriented education depends on creating a positive socio-educational environment, strengthening teacher-student interaction, and developing learners' self-regulation and self-assessment skills. Fundamental principles such as individuality, emotional-value orientation, and the subjectivity of the learning process are analyzed. The article concludes that personality-oriented teaching contributes to students' cognitive independence, motivation, and self-awareness, thereby improving the overall quality of education in primary schools.

Key words: personality-oriented education, primary school, pedagogical technology, individual development, socio-educational environment, teacher competence

The Essence and Importance of Personality-Oriented Education

The fundamental essence of personality-oriented education lies in the central role it assigns to the formation of the learner's personality. The entire learning process is focused on the upbringing and development of the student as an individual. Alongside all stages and levels of education, the organization and implementation of primary education on this basis and with such content constitutes one of the most significant pedagogical challenges of our time. Naturally, addressing this challenge depends on a range of factors and the fulfillment of specific conditions.

There are several factors that determine the implementation of a personality-oriented approach in primary education, which may be systematized as follows:

1. Rapid changes in modern society. Contemporary society is changing rapidly and continuously. Under these conditions, the issue of developing individuals capable of correctly perceiving themselves and the growing demands of society, possessing high moral qualities and ethical awareness, and being able to assess their own behavior adequately, becomes increasingly urgent. This creates the necessity of directing primary education towards the development of the learner's personality from the earliest grades.

2. The purpose of modern education. The aim of education today is not merely to fill students' minds with knowledge. Rather, its purpose is to provide learners with life experience, to foster their development, to reveal and cultivate their personal qualities. It seeks to nurture their thinking and imagination, and to shape them into active, creative, and independent individuals capable of self-directed activity in the future. The realization of these aims requires education to be fundamentally personality-oriented.

3. Limitations of traditional teaching methods. Traditional teaching methods are insufficient to meet the contemporary goals of educational development. Such methods often restrict students' preparation for active participation in social life. Therefore, education demands the adoption of more modern, student-

centered, and interactive methods that allow for the use of contemporary technological tools. These, in turn, inherently embody the principles of personality-oriented education.

4. Humanistic principles of modern education. Modern education is based on the principles of humanism, mutual respect between educators and learners, cooperation, and the treatment of learners as individual personalities. The establishment of education in primary schools upon a humanistic foundation is one of the key determinants of its effectiveness. Humanism in education is directly related to the development of personality and the recognition of the learner as an equal individual. Therefore, education implemented in this context functions as the guarantor of personality orientation. From this perspective, strengthening efforts toward the humanization of education emerges as a pressing pedagogical concern of our day.

5. Primary school students as future citizens. Today's primary school student is tomorrow's active citizen, a person who will represent Azerbaijan in various regions and countries. Ensuring that they possess high intellectual capacity, communication skills, and the motivation and ability for self-development, self-education, and self-actualization should occupy a central place in the content of contemporary education. Efforts toward these goals directly affect the learner's personality, thereby rendering personality-oriented education a pedagogical necessity. Consequently, it becomes essential to systematize the accumulated theoretical knowledge, organize classroom and extracurricular activities accordingly, and place the issue of personality formation at the core of the educational process.

According to the features of the personality-oriented education concept, the most important category that reveals the essence of this type of education is its content. The content of personality-oriented education is a system-forming element in the construction of the pedagogical process. The general methodological basis for developing the model of personality-oriented educational content is the orientation toward the effective development of the learner's personality as a subject of cognition, as well as the advancement of their life activity and culture as a whole. In this regard, the content of personality-oriented education must correspond to societal demands and the objective development of science and technology; it should serve as a means of self-development and self-education for the student and possess intrinsic value for them.

However, our observations and analyses reveal that there are considerable difficulties in organizing and implementing the process of self-education among primary school students. Primarily, they lack understanding of how, through what methods, and in what forms self-education can be carried out, and they require substantial support from teachers in this regard. Unfortunately, although teachers often give advice, they do not – or cannot – provide students with practical guidance on how and in what sequence to conduct the process. Professor M. Ilyasov writes:

«Education creates the conditions for the revelation and formation of learners' personal qualities. The educational process is not limited to the accumulation of knowledge in any field. As knowledge increases, it contributes to the emergence of certain personal qualities, serving as a kind of foundation. When properly organized, education exerts a stimulating influence through its internal order, fostering the development of a range of personal characteristics. It leads to the formation of moral, ethical, humanistic, aesthetic, industrious, and many other qualities» [6; 106].

The content of personality-oriented education must include not only subject-specific knowledge and skills but also creative experience and emotionally and value-based attitudes toward reality. For this reason, in the teaching process of primary grades, it is important to address the following essential pedagogical situations:

- engaging students in the independent acquisition of scientific knowledge and increasing the activity component of subject content;
- strengthening the role of theoretical knowledge by enabling students to understand the meaning of concepts and the reasons behind phenomena;
- establishing a consistent connection between theoretical content and practice;
- incorporating historical and scientific components into the learning material, revealing the cultural and value-based aspects of science, shaping students' worldviews, enhancing the humanitarian component of educational content, and transmitting universal values to them;
- presenting learning materials of varying complexity, volume, and form according to students' levels of comprehension;
- introducing students to the cultural characteristics and universal values of their own nation and other peoples of the world [4; 31–35].

The formation of the learner's personality within the learning process requires the application of personality-oriented or developmental educational technologies. During the implementation of developmental pedagogical technologies, the teacher indirectly supervises students' independent learning and research activities. The integration of developmental technologies into the teaching process ensures the following:

- comprehensive and effective development of the learner's personality, turning them into a subject of learning and cognition;
- formation of an emotional and value-based attitude toward the content of education;
- acquisition not only of knowledge, skills, and habits but also of ways of thinking and acting;
- development of creative abilities;
- cultivation of motivational needs within the learner's personality;
- enhancement of students' communication skills;
- provision of a differentiated approach based on students' intellectual development, level of preparedness, needs, and interests.

Personality-Oriented Pedagogical Technologies in Primary Education

Personality-oriented pedagogical technologies embody the principles of humanistic psychology and pedagogy in their most complete form. These technologies are developmental pedagogical methods based on active teaching strategies that ensure more effective personal development of students. The central concern here is that the teacher's attention is focused on the learner's personality – on developing not only memory but also creative and critical thinking, needs, motivation, communication skills, self-education, and self-development abilities. This, in turn, contributes not only to the formation of students' knowledge and skills but also to the development of creative thinking and self-improvement capacities. In this regard, the use of active learning methods plays an essential role.

When organizing the teaching process in primary school, teachers must also consider the objective factors influencing the effectiveness of modern educational technologies. These include the purpose of education, the development of communicative abilities in students, the consideration of their individual and age-specific characteristics, the methodological support of lessons, and the means of moral and personal education.

The use of active and interactive teaching methods in primary education implies students' joint learning and research activities, which in turn develop their ability to work collaboratively and communicate productively in groups. A personality-oriented situation, as an element of pedagogical technology, has its own distinct features. Taking these into account is essential in the implementation of personality-oriented pedagogical technologies.

In the pedagogical process, a personality-oriented situation presupposes the establishment of a purposeful and meaningful interaction among the subjects of the process. The goal of such a situation is to cultivate qualities such as individual selectivity, reasoning, and critical thinking in students, to help them draw conclusions from their experiences, recognize and correct their mistakes, and thereby create opportunities for personal growth. Thus, personality-oriented education functions as a tool for individual development.

Personality-oriented teaching technology is understood as the organization of students' activity around a topic through the adequate modification of learning situations. The implementation of such technology creates specific opportunities to work with the individual's personal experience.

In the classroom and, more broadly, in the teaching process as a whole, various methods and tools are employed to ensure the personality orientation of education. Among the methods applied in personality-oriented education, the following are especially notable: dialogue, simulation, modeling, role-play, life paradoxes, mental activity, and various designs of pedagogical conflict situations.

The main driving force behind ensuring the personality orientation of education in the classroom is the teacher and their possession of essential skills and competencies in this area. Although educational content may contain numerous nuances and moral potentials that could influence personality formation, without the teacher's proper guidance, interpretation, and analysis tailored to each student's interests and needs, their impact remains neutral. Therefore, it is crucial that teachers master personality-oriented educational technologies and are able to apply them creatively.

According to Professor İ. H. Cəbraylova, the successful implementation of learner-centered pedagogical technologies requires that teacher activity meet the following criteria:

- the teacher must possess an independent and free worldview;
- the teacher must skillfully use active teaching methods and work effectively with interactive strategies;
- the teacher must have the interdisciplinary knowledge and skills necessary to establish effective connections among subjects during lessons;
- the teacher must take into account and appropriately apply each student's individual and age characteristics [1; 18].

In addition, the following competencies are also considered essential:

- the teacher must possess strong communication skills and be able to establish professional interaction with students;
- the teacher must have a thorough understanding of the personality-oriented potential of each subject and topic taught and be able to convey these aspects to students during the learning process;

- the teacher must be able to «enter the learner's zone of proximal development» and influence their emotional sphere effectively.

Research shows that the most necessary condition for the successful implementation of personality-oriented education is the creation of a positive, developmental, social-educational environment within the educational institution. Many pedagogues argue that personality – as a quality of the human psyche – develops only when it engages in situations that allow for the manifestation of its specific functions of selection, reflection, meaning formation, will, self-regulation, social responsibility, creativity, and independence. From this perspective, special attention must first be given to the effective organization of the educational environment, since it represents not only a learning environment but also a specially designed educational space for mastering various forms and types of human activity. This space encompasses students' interpersonal communication, their emotionally and socially value-based relations with society, and their acquisition of both scientific knowledge and personal experience.

Personality-oriented education involves not only creating conditions for orienting the learning process toward the individual but also giving the learner's practical and social relationships a personality-centered character. The influence on personality development is only possible through the integration of all factors contributing to socialization. From this perspective, in personality-oriented education, «the consistent monitoring of quality management in the training of competent specialists in pedagogically oriented higher education institutions, the regular organization of diagnostic observations and expert evaluations, the timely identification of the pedagogical system's condition, and the implementation of appropriate corrective measures play a crucial role in achieving the main goal of our education system» [5; 211].

Particular attention should also be paid to the complex interaction between the school and the social environment. Schools, families, and public organizations must align their common educational and upbringing objectives, which will help transform the school into a social complex and an integral part of the educational system that ensures students' socialization.

Achieving personality-oriented education requires maintaining constant attention to this issue throughout the entire course of primary education. However, it should be emphasized that solving this problem is a gradual process – one that must take into account specific stages, each with its own content and significance. Professor Ə. Ə. Əlizadə emphasizes two particular stages: a) the stage of defining the learning task; b) the stage of «discovering» new knowledge.

In the stage of defining the learning task, the list of tasks should include a question that creates a conflict situation – that is, one that holds personal significance for the student and generates the need to comprehend the concept. In this process, the cognitive objective must be formulated clearly. The stage of «discovering» new knowledge is linked to problem-solving; during the process of inquiry and discussion, students engage in self-directed dialogue, while the teacher facilitates and, finally, summarizes the discussion [2]. At the initial stage, each required situation is explained by articulating aloud the established action algorithms (what we do, why we do it, and what is expected to be achieved). The effectiveness of the initial reinforcement depends on a complete presentation of the object's essential features, the modification of irrelevant ones, and the consolidation of instructional material through students' independent actions.

The task of the independent work phase in the classroom is to ensure students' self-monitoring and self-assessment. Self-monitoring teaches students to take responsibility for their work and to adequately evaluate the outcomes of their actions. Although actions during self-monitoring are initially accompanied by speech and verbal expression, they gradually shift to an internal level. At this stage, it is crucial to create a situation of success for each student («I can do it», «I am capable»). When working with new material, it is more efficient to implement the above-mentioned stages continuously within a single lesson. This usually takes about 20–25 minutes of the lesson. The remaining time is devoted to consolidating previously acquired knowledge and skills, integrating them with new material, and preparing for subsequent topics. During this time, errors identified in the self-monitoring stage are corrected. Such tasks generally have a productive nature.

During instructional exercises, the material studied in subsequent lessons is reinforced, reaching the level of automated mental activity, and cognitive renewal occurs. In a learner-centered lesson, the consolidation of knowledge takes place alongside the acquisition of new ideas, thereby expanding students' worldview. Therefore, it is necessary to incorporate new elements of knowledge into lessons. These may serve as anticipatory preparation for the systematic study of related topics or as a means for a deeper understanding of previously familiar material.

According to H.A. Alizade and P.M. Mahmudova, such a structure of lessons enables each student to progress at their individual pace: the more capable students receive additional «intellectual nourishment», while the weaker ones gain time to fully master the required material [3; 4–9].

Long-term research has made it possible, at the current stage of educational development, to identify several fundamental principles of learner-centered instruction, which constitute the basis of the school's teaching

process. It should be noted that in classifying these principles, the primary consideration has been given to the learner's personality and to basing instruction on individual characteristics. These principles are as follows:

- The principle of individual uniqueness and value. This implies recognizing the individuality and unique abilities of each child, affirming the necessity of constructing an educational process aimed at the maximum development of this individuality (entailing the development of flexible plans and programs tailored to the child's personal characteristics).
- The principle of the priority of individual development. Within the existing educational process of the school, the child's personal development is taken as the main driving link (here, education functions not as an end in itself but as a means of personal development).
- The principle of attention to the learner's zone of proximal development. This involves ensuring an attainable level of difficulty in mastering and structuring material together with the student (encompassing the classification of learning tasks according to the learner's individual pace and abilities).
- The principle of subjectivity in the learning process. This emphasizes orientation toward internal rather than external motivation (encouragement, avoidance of punishment) and presupposes granting the child freedom to choose spheres for applying their abilities in school life.
- The principle of emotionality and value orientation in the educational process. This implies the unity of the student's personal feelings and thoughts within the pedagogical process (maintaining a system of trustful and secure relationships, and designing curricula and programs that ensure maximum integration of knowledge), thereby achieving an emotionally holistic representation of the world.
- The principle of personal knowledge formation. This stimulates the didactic effect of knowledge formation (through the use of various pedagogical situations aimed at applying both subject-specific and interdisciplinary knowledge).

An educational process based on the above principles accepts the student as they are, perceiving them as an integral, holistic personality, and assists in their formation as a free, educated, responsible individual. In primary school, presenting several examples related to the problem at hand, arousing students' interest in the subject, using direct instructional appeals («we have obtained», «we see», «note», «translate», «decode» etc.), emphasizing that not only the teacher but also each student contributes to solving the problem, and demonstrating that the problem is resolved through collective inquiry and action – all of these stimulate students to think about the problem, its solution plan, and the result obtained. These are among the essential means of realizing the learner-centered nature of education. The teacher must emphasize that the solution is achieved through the collaborative efforts of all students and should provide each student with the opportunity to choose their own path to solving assigned tasks.

A number of effective methods used in the organization of the learner-centered approach can enable us to structure the process of learning and development in a way that allows the child to act more freely, with personal motivation, genuine interest, and initiative. For this purpose, primary school teachers must not only properly organize the students' activities in the classroom but also create a businesslike and productive learning environment. Under such conditions, an atmosphere of creativity, inquiry, and discovery will prevail. In the classroom, every child should feel confident that they are valued, loved, respected, and appreciated. Students will learn new things, analyze their own work and that of their peers, accurately identify the causes of failures, and evaluate their successes appropriately. Within such an environment, every child will work according to their creative potential, gain self-confidence, and experience the joy of accomplishment. As a result, the student will develop a deeper appreciation for learning and for the acquisition of knowledge.

Therefore, the teacher's responsibility is to create a comfortable learning atmosphere in the classroom, to engage students in active learning, to make the learning process interesting and accessible for every child, and to identify the methods and means to achieve these goals. At this stage of social development, the priority for primary education lies in organizing learning activities that cultivate in students both the desire and the ability to learn, promote their formation as individuals, develop their cognitive interests, and prepare them for high-level learning. At the same time, the teacher should foster in students a sense of need for self-education and self-discipline. In a modern school, the teacher must fulfill the function of designing each student's individual intellectual development.

Our research, which characterizes the provision of learner-centeredness in the educational process as a key factor in the development of the learner's personality, demonstrates that the achievement of educational goals in contemporary primary education largely depends on the learning technologies employed to ensure learner-centered instruction. In our view, the use of learner-centered learning technologies in this direction can yield the following expected outcomes:

1. The student is placed in an environment that constantly requires activity, independent decision-making, and overcoming emerging difficulties.
2. Conditions are created to eliminate the stereotypes of traditional teaching. The educational process

is organized as a humanistic interaction between teacher and students, wherein the student becomes the subject of learning.

3. Favorable conditions are created for self-knowledge, self-improvement, and self-education.
4. Student engagement increases, and even the weakest learners participate in meaningful activities.
5. A favorable atmosphere for learning emerges, motivating students to learn with greater enthusiasm.
6. Alongside the promotion of learning interest, conditions are created for the development of students' creative abilities.
7. Teacher–student and student–student collaboration reaches its highest level, fostering the development of collectivism.
8. The educational and formative potential of the lesson becomes evident, expanding opportunities for students' personal development.

Learner-centered instruction plays a crucial role in the further advancement of the educational system. Naturally, it reflects the existing changes in the learning process of young pupils and provides a powerful impetus for their preparation for independent and conscious activity. In primary education, «the learner-centeredness of instruction is closely linked to pedagogical professionalism and competence. The teacher must, above all, have a thorough understanding of the subject being taught – including its educational, formative, and developmental potential. They must be aware of students' potential abilities, seek out effective ways to foster their thinking, initiative, and activity, and ensure that the subject matter and individual topics correspond to the students' moral and intellectual needs» [7; 107].

In our opinion, modern education should not be limited to the implementation of the State Educational Standard; rather, it must be directed toward the development of the human personality, the revelation of individual capacities and talents, and the formation of self-awareness. This approach enables the school to prepare competent graduates capable of navigating the rapidly evolving, technologically advanced informational environment.

At present, considerable attention is paid in school practice to the use of learner-centered teaching technologies in primary education. These changes are driven by the active modernization of contemporary education, which imposes higher demands on the professional qualities of modern teachers. Nevertheless, the traditional practices of the existing educational system partly contradict these newly established theoretical orientations. One reason for this contradiction lies in the persistence of «subject–object» relations among participants in the learning process within the conservative, classroom-based instructional system.

Since the teacher's daily pedagogical activity in changing conditions involves the continuous resolution of organizational, methodological, and educational tasks, the application of learner-centered teaching technologies in primary grades requires taking into account the motivational foundations of student activity. Considering the motivational and value-based components of educational content at the instructional level contributes to students' engagement in learning and helps them perceive social and personal meaning in the acquired knowledge, processes, and events – ultimately enhancing the quality of education.

Thus, our analysis and generalizations demonstrate that ensuring the learner-centered nature of education in primary schools cannot rely solely on pedagogical factors (such as the teacher's knowledge of learner-centered instruction or their professional competence in its application). A range of psychological factors (e.g., psychological support, teacher–student relationships) and social factors (e.g., creation of a favorable educational environment, humanistic values in the pedagogical process), as well as other related aspects, play equally significant roles. Therefore, a creative approach by every primary school teacher – taking into account these factors – can greatly contribute to achieving learner-centered education and to successfully realizing the objectives set within this framework.

References

1. Cəbrayılov İ.H. Şəxsiyyətyönümlü təhsil və vətəndaş cəmiyyəti. Bakı : Mütərcim, 2011. 216 s.
2. Əlizadə Ə. Ə. Seçilmiş əsərləri. I cild. Bakı : Füyuzat, 2022. 524 s.
3. Əlizadə H. Ə., R.M. Mahmudova Sosial pedaqogika. Dərslük. Bakı : BDU, 2013. 412 s.
4. Mehrabov A. O., Abbasov Ə.Ə. Pedaqoji texnologiyalar [və b.] Bakı : Mütərcim, 2006. 282 s.
5. Mehrabov A. O. Səriştəli müəllim hazırlığının problemləri. Bakı : Elm və təhsil, 2015. 288 s.
6. İlyasov M.İ. Müasir təhsil: ənənədən innovasiyaya. Bakı : Elm və təhsil, 2021. 376 s.
7. İlyasov M. İ. Müəllim peşəkarlığı və pedaqoji səriştəliliyin müasir problemləri. Bakı : Elm və təhsil, 2018. 208 s.
8. Bayramov H. B. Ali məktəbdə didaktika: Nəzəri-praktik kreativlər. Bakı : APOSTROF-A, 2023. 260 s.
9. Sadıqov F.B. Ümumi pedaqogika. Bakı : Maarif nəşriyyatı, 2023. 852 s.

УДК: 373.3:37.015.3

ОСНОВНІ ФАКТОРИ, ЩО ВИЗНАЧАЮТЬ ОСОБИСТІСТЬ-ОРІЄНТОВАНИЙ ПЕДАГОГІЧНИЙ ПРОЦЕС У ПОЧАТКОВІЙ ОСВІТІ

Зейналова Аїда БАБАК – докторант, Азербайджанський державний педагогічний університет, Баку

Розглядається сутність та механізми впровадження особистісно-орієнтованих освітніх технологій у навчанні початкової школи. Підкреслюється, що забезпечення особистісно-орієнтованого підходу в процесі навчання вимагає від вчителя педагогічної компетентності, творчої активності та здатності адаптувати зміст навчання до індивідуальних потреб та особливостей розвитку учнів. У дослідженні наголошується, що ефективна реалізація особистісно-орієнтованої освіти залежить від створення позитивного соціально-освітнього середовища, зміцнення взаємодії вчителя та учня, розвитку навичок саморегуляції та самооцінки учнів. Аналізуються такі фундаментальні принципи, як індивідуальність, емоційно-ціннісна орієнтація та суб'єктивність процесу навчання. Зроблено висновок, що особистісно-орієнтоване навчання сприяє когнітивній самостійності, мотивації та самосвідомості учнів, тим самим покращуючи загальну якість освіти в початкових школах.

Ключові слова: особистісно-орієнтоване навчання, початкова школа, педагогічні технології, індивідуальний розвиток, соціально-освітнє середовище, компетентність учителя.

Стаття отримана 31.08. 2025

Стаття прийнята 22.10. 2025

Опублікована 26.12. 2025

UDC 372.851

WAYS AND METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT WORK IN PRIMARY CLASSES BASED ON MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

Sabina Seyidli HAMZA – Doctoral Student, Azerbaijan
State Pedagogical University

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1552-7499>

doi

sabinasq77@gmail.com

This article examines the development of students' independent activity, logical and creative thinking, and research skills in primary school mathematics instruction. The author notes that the primary goal of modern education is not simply the transfer of knowledge, but the development of students as individuals, with independent thinking and decision-making skills. Based on curriculum requirements, the use of interactive and student-centered methods, observation, problem-solving, question-and-answer models, and independent and creative assignments stimulates students' cognitive activity. The article demonstrates that by organizing independent work in mathematics lessons, students acquire knowledge through discovery, which develops their long-term memory and analytical and critical thinking. During the teaching process, teachers must consider the individual characteristics of each student and create conditions for them to freely express their opinions. The author concludes that the use of modern educational technologies has a significant impact on the development of mathematical thinking, independence, and research skills in primary school students.

Key words: teaching mathematics, elementary grades, independent work, interactive methods, research skills, logical thinking, creative thinking, cognitive activity.

Introduction. Today, the implementation of modern education in schools, including subject-based curricula, serves a specific purpose, which is the primary outcome of education. To achieve positive educational outcomes, it is essential to use an interactive teaching method. Interactive teaching fosters independence and life skills in students, creating ample opportunities for their personal development. We know from the experience of comprehensive schools that today's approach to education and students in comprehensive schools has radically and fundamentally changed. Teachers are not content simply imparting knowledge to students; they also strive to shape their worldview and intellectual development. In other words, preparing students for independent living has become the primary goal of student-centered education. The development of thinking plays a crucial and effective role in students' development as individuals. We know that subject-based curricula have been used in grades 1-4 since 2007. One of the main goals of the subject-based curriculum is the development and formation of students' logical, cognitive thinking. True, such issues were always a focus for teachers in the post-Soviet period, but the primary requirement of the curriculum at that time was simply to provide students with knowledge. At that time, preparing students as research participants was considered secondary.

As a result, students weren't fully consciously aware of the theoretical and practical issues being studied, and memorization took precedence. Knowledge acquired in this way was not long-lasting [4; 801-822]. Consequently, students studied only science, but their logical thinking was not developed as effectively. In traditional learning,